

CHARACTERIZATION OF UNDAMAGED AND DAMAGED CARBON FIBER COMPOSITES IN ELECTROMAGNETIC FIELDS FOR INDUCTIVE CHARGING OF ELECTRIC VEHICLES

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ABSTRACT

Inductive charging improves convenience for the drivers of electric cars. Next-generation contactless technology for inductive charging will require a copper coil on the receiver end, which is to be structurally integrated into the electric vehicle's underbody. The anisotropic electrical and mechanical properties of carbon fiber reinforced polymers (CFRPs) could allow the use in electromagnetic fields. A basic understanding of CFRP in electromagnetic fields was gained by characterizing carbon fiber loops featuring different sizes, geometries and fiber materials. The anisotropic specific conductivity was measured to better understand the current flow inside CFRP plates.

Since CFRPs are being considered for use as structural material for the inductive charging units in the underfloor of cars, impact damage caused by stones is another topic of concern.

Therefore, damaged and undamaged CFRP plates were placed inside the electromagnetic field of a Helmholtz-coil setup to measure the eddy current behaviour and the changes in current flow after an impact.

Finally, a carbon-fiber sensor network is being studied to monitor the inductive charging process by measuring the electromagnetic flux density as well as the overall temperature and impact damage.

1 INTRODUCTION

Due to the increasing adoption of electric vehicles, the automotive industry is thinking about new charging methods. Contactless inductive charging requires no charging cable, which makes the process more convenient for the driver. Between the primary coil in the ground and the secondary coil in the vehicle's underbody, the power is transferred through an alternating electromagnetic field at frequencies of about 83 *kHz* [1]. One remaining challenge is the mechanical integration of the secondary coil into the underbody [2]. A possible solution can be seen in Figure 1 which shows a vehicle on which the inductive charging unit has been mounted in the front section of the underbody.

The structural integration of the secondary coil has to meet several requirements, like high strength and stiffness as well as low weight and high thermal conductivity [3, 4].

Glass and carbon fiber reinforced polymers (CFRPs) are being investigated for use as potential structural materials [5, 6]. Before CFRPs can be used, a basic understanding of how the electrically conductive carbon fibers behave inside the electromagnetic field is needed.

The electromagnetic properties of CFRPs are already being investigated for non-destructive testing (NDT) and the joining process of thermoplastic CFRP. One example is detection of structural damage, such as fiber breakage and delamination, through induced eddy currents [7, 8]. Another is the use of induction heating in order to weld thermoplastic carbon fiber composites [9]. However, the

frequencies and field strengths that were used differ from the inductive charging unit's electromagnetic field. Also, other investigations have not looked into possibilities for reducing the current flow, which is a key area of interest in this investigation.

Figure 1: Front section of an electric vehicle's underbody with a structurally integrated inductive charging unit.

In a first step, basic electric and electromagnetic properties of carbon fibers and of CFRP plates were to be investigated with regard to the inductive charging unit application. Carbon fiber loops were used to determine the influence of the material and the geometric parameters when voltages and currents are induced. The anisotropic specific conductivities enabled a better understanding of how currents flow inside CFRP plates.

As a next step, damaged and undamaged CFRP probes were placed into the electromagnetic field of a Helmholtz-coil setup in order to measure the effects of eddy currents inside the material. A drop weight impactor was used to simulate characteristic damage from stones.

In previous investigations, it was demonstrated that carbon fiber sensors can be used for structural health monitoring (SHM) and temperature measurements [10, 11]. A new approach was studied, in order to use a carbon fiber sensor network for monitoring the charging process with regard to the homogeneity of the electromagnetic field, the position of the secondary coil in relation to the primary coil as well as the overall temperature of the structural CFRP component and impact damages. A monitoring system like this could be beneficial for autonomous vehicles.

The carbon fiber materials described in Table 1 were used together with an epoxy or polyurethane matrix system.

Fiber material	Manufacturer	Type	Roving size	Surface weight
ex-PAN	Toho-Tenax	HTA40	1 - 12 k	-
ex-PAN	SGL	C T50-4.4/255-E100	50 k	300 g/m ²
ex-PAN	NGF	CN-60	3 k	-
ex-pitch	Mitsubishi	Dialead K63712	12 k	250 g/m ²
ex-PAN (Ni-coated)	Toho-Tenax	HTS40 MC	12 k	(600 g/m ²)
				Fabricated out of 12 k rovings

Table 1: The carbon fiber materials used in this investigation.

2 MEASURING METHODS

2.1 RESISTANCE MEASUREMENTS

Quadratic one- and two-ply probes (30 x 30 and 50 x 50 mm) were made to measure the directional electrical resistances of the CFRP laminates. Two main methods were applied as shown in Figure 2.

One method used silver paint to electrically connect the measuring equipment to the probes. Sanding down the top surfaces removed the covering epoxy matrix above the carbon fibers, which then allowed contact.

A second method established the electrical contact by inserting a copper wire into the dry carbon fiber tows or by placing a copper mesh (Bender AEROMESH ECF Ae73) onto the top and bottom surfaces before laminating the probes. (This allowed contact points between the copper and the carbon fibers, which were then held in place by the epoxy matrix after laminating.) Abrading was used to remove epoxy material to allow for soldering of the copper.

Figure 2: The contacting methods with the conductive silver paint and copper wire/mesh for resistance measurements in the transverse (above) and through-thickness direction (below).

The resistance was measured with the LCR meter (Hameg HM 8018) at a frequency of 1 kHz using a two-wire measuring circuit. The results were converted for better comparability to specific conductivities using equation 1.

$$\sigma = l/(R A) \quad (1)$$

With the specific conductivity σ , l and A as the length and cross-sectional area and the measured resistance R .

Both contact methods were applied on 10 identical probes with a size of 30 x 30 mm for resistance measurements in the through-thickness and transverse directions. For the respective measuring direction, the mean values deviated less than 2.4 % from each other with comparable standard deviations. Since both methods produce similar results, the ones with copper wire/mesh were preferred because they were faster to manufacture.

2.2 MEASUREMENTS IN THE ELECTROMAGNETIC

The homogeneous electromagnetic field in the middle of a Helmholtz-coil setup with a coil diameter of 485 mm was used in either a single-coil or dual-coil setup. The induced voltages and currents were measured using an oscilloscope (InfiniiVision MSO7014B) or a multimeter (Agilent U1241A). The field strength varied between 125 and 900 μT at frequencies of 83 to 115 kHz . To avoid induced voltages, a coaxial cable was used to connect the measurement equipment to the probes. In order to characterize the basic behavior of the carbon fibers in the electromagnetic field, quadratic and rectangular loops with sizes of 40 x 40, 60 x 60, 80 x 80 and 20 x 110 mm were made with carbon fiber tows of 1,000 - 24,000 filaments with the ex-PAN, ex-pitch and ex-PAN-Ni-coated carbon fiber materials summarized in Table 1. For comparative purposes, a copper loop with the dimensions of 60 x 60 mm was used. The ends of the carbon fiber loops were soldered after applying a galvanic process as described in [12]. The use of a 10 Ω resistor made it possible to precisely constrain the current flow inside the loops (Figure 3). It was possible to calculate the resistance of the loops

inside the electromagnetic field by measuring the induced voltages and currents. The calculated resistance could then be compared to a resistance measurement outside of the electromagnetic field with the LCR-meter setup already mentioned above.

The behavior of CFRP laminates was characterized using quadratic probes of a size between 80×80 and 120×120 mm, consisting of 8-16 plies with the UD materials described in Table 1. The probes were placed into the electromagnetic field with a dual-coil setup, and the change in electromagnetic flux density was measured using a coil with an inner diameter of 32 mm and 80 turns. The rise in temperature was measured using a PT-100 temperature sensor, which was connected to the HBM Quantum MX1615 measuring amplifier. The use of thermography with the thermal imaging camera (Flir ThermoCAM S60) allowed for a visual inspection of the heat distribution. The probes were exposed to an electromagnetic field at 83 kHz with field strength of $600 \mu T$ for 20 seconds. Further evaluation of the thermal images was possible by using Matlab to better analyze the current flow.

Figure 3: The Helmholtz-coil setup for characterizing the carbon fiber loops.

2.2 DROP WEIGHT IMPACT MEASUREMENT

To damage the CFRP probes, the impact setup seen in Figure 4 was used. The setup followed the “Boeing BSS 7260” standard [13]. The impactor had a weight of 1.7 kg and a tip diameter of 16 mm. The probes with dimensions of 100×100 mm were made out of 12 layers of the UD ex-PAN fiber material. They were impacted with three energy levels of 13.2, 19.8 and 26.4 J in the middle of the probe as well as in a “corner” position at the top right corner with 10 mm from the edges of the probes. An impact at the “corner” position is quite different from state-of-the-art impact testing but was chosen after examining the thermography images to damage the probes at a high current density position. The fixation of the probes was accomplished using 80×80 mm aluminum profiles with two clamping ledges held down by bolts.

Figure 4: The impact setup used for damaging the CFRP probes.

After impacting, the probes were characterized in the electromagnetic field as described above.

2.3 CARBON FIBER SENSOR NETWORK

For carbon fiber sensors, loops with sizes of $10 \times 100 \text{ mm}$ and $40 \times 100 \text{ mm}$ were made out of a 1k ex-PAN HTA40 fiber tow. The electrical contact was established as already described in chapter 2.2. One probe consisted of three loops of the same size, which were laminated on top of four plies of a 220 g/m^2 [0/90] glass fiber material. The arrangement of three parallel sensor loops should make it possible to measure the electromagnetic flux density distribution of the electromagnetic field. They were placed in the electromagnetic field of the Helmholtz-coil setup similar to Figure 3 but in a dual-coil configuration with a field strength of $600 \mu\text{T}$ and a frequency of 83 kHz . The induced voltages were measured with the “InfiniiVision MSO7014B” oscilloscope. To simulate the autonomous positioning of a charging unit, the probe was moved from the center to the outside of the lower Helmholtz-coil.

3 RESULTS

3.1 BASIC ELECTRIC AND ELECTROMAGNETIC PROPERTIES

In Figure 5, the induced electrical values of two ex-PAN (neat and Ni-coated) and an ex-pitch carbon fiber loop as well as a copper loop can be seen. All loops consist of a 12k-roving, have a square geometry with the size of $60 \times 60 \text{ mm}$ and were characterized in an electromagnetic field at a field strength of $335 \mu\text{T}$ and a frequency of 115 kHz . With respect to the measuring accuracy, it can be seen that the induced no-load voltage is the same for all loops. Also, the loops show good linear behavior when current is flowing.

Figure 5: Induced voltages and currents of the $60 \times 60 \text{ mm}$ loops with different carbon fiber materials and a copper loop for reference.

Figure 6 shows the percentage of the ohmic resistance on the behavior in the electromagnetic field for the loops seen in Figure 5 and for different ex-PAN roving sizes with a loop size of $60 \times 60 \text{ mm}$, which were characterized in the same electromagnetic field.

The ohmic resistance plays, with the exception of the Ni-coated carbon fiber and the copper loop, a major role ($> 92 \%$) on the electromagnetic behavior of the loops. It can be seen that the share of the unspecified effect grows when the amount of the ohmic resistance decreases. The ohmic resistance can be calculated by transforming equation 1.

When compared to the copper loop, it does not appear as if there were any major electromagnetic effects specific to the carbon fibers. The increase in the share of the unspecified resistance is partly due to the opposing electromagnetic field created by the flowing currents in the loops, which reduces the induced voltages. With regard to the parameters used in these investigations, it can be stated that the carbon fibers follow Maxwell’s equations, which describe the relations between electromagnetic fields applied and induced electrical values. Skin or proximity effects are not dominating the behavior for the investigated frequencies.

Figure 6: The percentage of the ohmic resistance on the resistance in the electromagnetic field for the loop size of 60 x 60 mm with different carbon fiber materials and roving sizes.

Figure 7 shows the measured specific conductivity values. The probes with the “glass” indication have an isolating glass fiber layer between the carbon fiber plies.

Figure 7: The specific conductivities of the CFRP probes of different carbon fiber materials and probes with an insulating glass fiber layer when measured in the transverse and through-thickness direction.

When compared to the specific conductivity in the fiber direction ($\sim 6 \cdot 10^4 \text{ S/m}$ for the ex-PAN), the specific conductivity in the transverse and through-thickness directions are, by a factor of $> 7,000$, much smaller and can therefore be considered to be close to equal. The measured values in the through-thickness direction don't change significantly between the ex-PAN probes with one and two plies or the change in fiber angle to 90° for the second ply. The specific conductivities in the transverse and through-thickness directions rise with the specific conductivity in the fiber direction, which can be seen for the ex-pitch and Ni-coated ex-PAN probes. The measured values for the “glass” probes drop significantly by a factor of ~ 300 when compared to the respective probe with no glass fiber layer. This insulation effect is of great interest when CFRP is used in the inductive charging unit to constrain eddy currents.

3.2 DAMAGED AND UNDAMAGED CFRP PROBES

Figure 8 shows the behavior of several undamaged CFRP probes with a size of 100 x 100 mm and 12 plies. The shielding rate decreases the efficiency of the charging process, while the heating rate reflects the temperature increase during charging.

Figure 8: The measured electromagnetic behavior of undamaged CFRP probes with different fiber materials and laminate layups.

There is a correlation between the shielding rate and the heating rate. Both rates result from the induced eddy currents. The scale of the shielding and heating rates are influenced by the specific conductivity as well as by the stacking sequence and the fiber angles. The induced eddy currents grow when the changes in the fiber angle become more frequent and more pronounced. The greatest values appear for the ex-pitch probe with a laminate layup of $[(0/90)_3]_{\text{sym}}$, a heating rate of 0.52 K/s and a shielding rate of 14.2 %. Since the corresponding ex-PAN probe had lower values, the rise in shielding and heating rate can be attributed to the higher specific conductivity of the ex-pitch in comparison to the ex-PAN fiber material. An insulating glass fiber layer between carbon fiber plies of different angles ($[0_3/Gl./90_3]_{\text{sym}}$ laminate) was able to reduce the shielding and heating rates to values too small to measure accurately, showing the potential of optimization.

Figure 9 shows the behavior of four 100 x 100 mm $[0/90]_{\text{sym}}$ ex-PAN probes before and after impact. The probes were impacted with energy levels of 19.8 and 26.4 J in the middle and “corner” positions.

Figure 9: The electromagnetic shielding of the probes when measured at the opposite corner of impact.

At 0.90 ± 0.015 K/s the heating rates at the edges remained on the same level for all probes before

and after the impact. While the shielding in the middle of the probes also stayed constant at $11 \pm 0.5 \%$, the shielding rates increased significantly at the corner when impacted at the corner position.

Figure 10 shows a microscopy image of the impacted specimen, where broken fibers can be seen in the 0° -ply. The thermography images in Figure 11 also indicates a change in the current path. Before the impact, the edges of the probe were about 4°C warmer than the middle of the probe. Four hot spots can be seen at the respective center of the outer edges. After the impact, the cooler rectangular shape in the middle was more pronounced and extended outwards, in particular at the impact position.

Figure 10: A microscopy image of a $[0/90]_{\text{sym}}$ probe after a 26.4 J impact at the corner position.

Figure 11: Thermography images of a $[0/90]_{\text{sym}}$ probe after 20 s in the electromagnetic field before (left) and after (right) a 26.4 J impact at the “corner” position.

Within the measuring accuracy, the overall absorbed power did not appear to change.

3.2 SENSOR NETWORK

Referring to the aim of autonomous positioning of vehicles for optimum charging conditions, the probes were placed in the center of the coil and were then moved towards the coil windings in 20 mm steps. The signal seen in Figure 12 indicates the optimum charging position for the electric vehicle. While the smaller carbon fiber loops barley show any changes in their induced voltages, the increase in the induced voltages just above of the Helmholtz-coil winding can be clearly detected for the bigger carbon fiber loops. This is due to the higher signal level, which can be measured more accurately in the chosen setup.

In a further step, a carbon fiber loop configuration will be developed to measure not only the distance from the center of the Helmholtz coil but also the xy -position. A new experimental setup will be able to characterize the ability of the carbon fiber loops to measure the overall temperature of the structural CFRP component during charging. In combination with the potential of SHM, the charging process of autonomous vehicles can be safely monitored.

Figure 12: The induced voltages in the sensor loops when moved from the center to the outside.

4. CONCLUSION

The results showed that the carbon fiber tows follow Maxwell's equations in the electromagnetic field with good accuracy for the parameters used. The lower specific conductivity of the ex-PAN fibers in comparison to the ex-pitch fibers can be seen by a greater drop in voltage when currents are flowing. Using new contacting methods, the anisotropic conductivities of UD-layers were characterized, which are decisive for the development of eddy currents. The investigation showed, that the conductivity in the through-thickness direction is 47 to 60 % lower than in the transverse direction. Using a glass fiber layer makes it possible to lower the specific conductivity in the through-thickness direction significantly.

The energy absorbed by CFRP plates can be influenced by parameters like the frequency of the change in fiber angle, the stacking sequence and the specific conductivity of the fiber material. Therefore, layers of different fiber orientation should be grouped together or insulated by a glass fiber layer. The investigation of impact damage shows that the current flow can be affected remarkably which can be seen by an increase of the shielding rate at the “corner” position by a factor of > 3. It has been shown that the position of impact in relation to the overall geometry of the CFRP probe is of relevance. Since eddy currents develop at the outer area of the specimens, the influence of impacts at the “corner” position have a stronger effect on the shielding rates than impacts at the center.

Carbon fiber sensor network has the potential for enabling reliable autonomous charging process monitoring. The carbon fiber network can be applied to optimize the position of the charging unit, to control thermal hotspots during charging and to detect impact damages.

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